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Research Article

Dietary Patterns, Risk Factors, Trends & Incidence of Gastrointestinal Tract Cancers in Kashmir Region of India

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ABSTRACT

Background: Cancer is a multifaceted and complex disease, which is defined as, a rapid and abnormal divisions of cells which engulfs other organs in a process of metastasis. Gastrointestinal cancers are prevalent in Kashmir and new cases are rising drastically, it's because of unawareness of food habits, smoking, snuffing, spraying of orchards without proper protocols, unhealthy lifestyles, wazwan (non-vegetarian foods), red meat consumption, processed and ultra processed foods, micro plastics, harmful radiations. Gastrointestinal cancers encompass a group of cancers that affect the digestive system. It is noted that Kashmir valley has cancer patients at highest number as compared to rest of India, being a union territory of India, Kashmiri people are unaware about the healthy lifestyle and health care system. Due to lack of knowledge of healthy life style & food habits it has become burden on government run hospitals to come out of this mess, although treatment regarding cancer is par with other Indian hospitals, but there is lack of concept of dietician & nutritionists. Aims/Objectives: The main objective of this research is to study the dietary patterns of the Kashmiri people, risk factors due to which cancer is occurring in Kashmir region and the trends and incidence rate of gastrointestinal tract cancers in Kashmir region. Results: This study was conducted in Super speciality hospital department of medical oncology GMC Srinagar. Qualitative data both questionnaire and interview method was used. Sample of 100 cancer patients was taken for the study. Results of this study have shown that dietary patterns and life style of Kashmiris, is the main reason of occurring cancer in

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this region. Out of 100 patients possible risk factors were smoking both hookah and cigarette, majority were eating red meat, smoked non-vegetarian like barbeque of meat, fish and chicken, sedentary lifestyle, snuffing, unprotected spraying chemicals and fertilizers of orchards, delayed treatment because majority of patients were taking palliative care
Conclusion: This study has concluded that the incidence rate of cancer can be controlled by following a proper diet. The broader part of this study is in progress.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a non-transmissible disease. Over three-fifths of demises worldwide are caused by non-transmissible diseases. Cancer is rapidly emerging disease in past few years. Incidence of new cancer cases rising day by day all over the world. According to the latest statistics, over 10 million people die yearly due to cancer and 70% of them are from developing countries. Gastrointestinal cancers encompass a group of cancers that effect the digestive system. These cancers can arise in various parts of the gastrointestinal tract (GI) including the oesophagus, GEJ Junction, stomach, colon, rectum, gallbladder and pancreas. While some GI cancers are more common, such as oesophagus, stomach, colorectal cancer. Cancer is an uncontrollable and irregular cell division in a definite portion of the body that can spread to other parts (metastasis). The main causes of GI tract cancers are consumption of beef (non-vegetarian), smoking both active & passive, high consumption of tea particularly pink tea or noon-chai, use of chemicals, preservatives, synthetic colorants & dyes, adulterated spices like meta nil in turmeric, unpredictable genetic changes, environmental factors. The main reasons for increasing incidence rate of cancer cases are certain lifestyle choices like consuming unhealthy foods, lack of physical activities, obesity and exposure to harmful pollutants. Diagnosis of cancer involves a comprehensive approach (biochemical assessment like blood tests like CBCs, LFTs, KFTs, tumour markers screening (CEA, CA-19-9, Ca-125,

endoscopy, CT-SCAN, endoscopic biopsy. Mostly GI Tract cancers are of adenocarcinoma (mucosa layer producing mucus), type. Diagnosis of cancer in early stage is difficult and very few cases are diagnosed because cancer in early stage is painless which patients usually ignores that's why delayed treatment is one of the factors of progress of cancer which by then metastasise in many patients. The main symptoms are: dysphagia, anaemia, frequent burps, blood tarry stools, uncontrolled pain in later stage, diarrhoea, ascites, hurt burn, stomach ache, vomiting etc. Kashmir is located at very high altitude in the northernmost extreme part of India. It is also northern most Union Territory of India. Kashmir's weather conditions, food habits, culture, customs and values are different from rest of India. Kashmir has Muslim majority population having unique cultural and traditional practices, beautiful hilly terrain, snow covered deep valleys and rich flora and fauna. The total population of Kashmir region is 6907623 approximately as per the 2011 census. From 2018-19 to 2023-24, the total number of cancer patients in Kashmir is approximately 80000. It's through the National Cancer Control Program, "SKIMS (Sher-Kashmir Institute of medical sciences)", a cancer referral centre delivering facilities to entire Kashmir, was freshly selected as a regional. Cancer can be detected by endoscopy and biopsy. The age group in which cancer is frequently occurring is 65-74 for males and 55 to 64 for females. Gastrointestinal cancer is highly predominant in the Kashmir region as compared to the other parts of the country.

Trends of cancer in Kashmir region

Worldwide, an increase in the incidence of cancer has also become evident for the population of Kashmir who have suffered from cancer in the last years. Kashmir's Regional Cancer Centre is the only one that maintains the number of cancer

patients. From the year 2018-2021, 22002 persons died due to cancer at Sher-e-Kashmir Medical Institute, Saura, Kashmir. From the above number of patients, 4.5, 31 and 32% of the deaths occurred in 2018, 2019, and 2020, respectively. In the year 2021, the number of deaths due to cancer increased to 7189. Here are some of the trends in cancer from different years (Table 1).

Table 1 Trends of cancer cases in Kashmir region from 2016 to 2022

Year	Sher - I-Kashmir, Institute of Medical Sciences		
	Cases of cancer	Deaths due to cancer	Follow up
2016	4800	NA	70000 patients of cancer taking follow up of their treatment
2018	NA	986	
2019	Breast=	6824	
2020	351	7003	
2021	Lung = 501 Thyroid= 221	7189	
2022	5284	1110	

Source: Qadri et al. (2023)

Observations:

Present study was conducted in Medical Oncology department of Super Speciality Hospital department of medical oncology Govt. Medical College Srinagar. A sample of 100 patients was taken for study. Researcher himself visited the hospital and an interview and questionnaire methods were adopted for the study. The main concern was to know the lifestyle and dietary habits of the patients, as a result the main contributory reasons for this disease were came in to light. Recent years, cancer is spreading like a wildfire due to increasing vendors, restaurants in Kashmir. The vendors and restaurants using synthetic colourants, decomposed meat, meat from those animals which are prohibited because scientifically they are not fit to eat and also ways of cutting and import from other states of India as

because halal method is better than jhatka method. In halal method microbial growth is less as compared to jhatka meat. Due to this incidence rate is increasing and hospital are receiving patients in huge numbers. In Kashmir incidence rate of gastrointestinal tract cancer is higher as compared to other states because of eating more non-vegetarian food by Kashmiri people as compared to other states people. Due to this growing rate government is now on foot to crack down on storage houses of edible food products which were found unhygienic and decomposed. Cancer a bomb is exploding in every corner and districts of Kashmir. As we have taken 100 patients it was found that different contributory reasons for cancer.

Smoked foods

Smoked foods barbeques like meat, chicken fish, pickles and salted foods: Patients were taking high consumption of salted foods like nun chai (salted tea, a combination of salt & sodium bicarbonate), pickled vegetables and processed meat. This is one of the main reasons of growing gastrointestinal cancer in Kashmir region.

Low consumption of fruits and vegetables

The patient's diet was not including fruits and vegetables which was a reason for higher risk for gastrointestinal cancer.

Consumption red meat:

The selected patients were taking red meat in their diet. Its high consumption leads to increase in the risk of stomach cancer.

Lack of physical activity and sedentary lifestyle

As Kashmir experiences heavy snowfall in winter season and temperature drops to below zero degrees. The patients in the present study were not

doing any physical activity. And thus, lack of physical activity contributes to the reasons of growing cancer in Kashmir region.

Smoking (Hukkah and Cigarette):

The use of hukkah is very much prevalent in rural Kashmir region. Smoking is of two types active smoking as well as passive smoking. The patients in present study were consuming hukkah and cigarette in their daily life means they were active smokers while patients belong to the category of passive smokers as well while they were inhaling the smoke by coming in to the contact of their family members because in winters due to very low temperature doors and windows of the houses are keep shut and there is no fresh air entering in to the house. This habit highly leads to the reason for growing cancer in Kashmir region.

Delayed treatment:

In rural Kashmir people are not aware of the treatment of the diseases. There is a delayed diagnosis for many of the diseases. The patients in present study were illiterate. And due the low literacy rate in this region of India, people are not aware about various diseases. At first, they totally ignore the disease and at later stage it becomes problematic sometimes diagnostic errors, diagnosis errors well

Eating excessive non-vegetarian food

Rice is staple food of Kashmir but eating excessive non-vegetarian particularly beef, dried fishes along with rice is one of the reasons for causing cancer in Kashmir. Patients in present study were taking non-vegetarian in their food making it as the main possible reason for cancer.

Wazwan:

Wazwan a both vegetarian and non-vegetarian food (Synthetic Colourants, excessive flavouring agents like monosodium glutamate). patients were taking wazwan occasionally but it increased since from last 5 years. This also increases the risk for cancer.

Adulterated spices

Use of adulterated spices having potential carcinogens leads to cancer, as spices are present in every household. Very few patients were consuming whole spices

High consumption of refined cereals and oils

Use of excess refined oils is also a main reason of cancer in Kashmir region.

Micro-plastics

microplastics is also now becoming a major reason for growing cancer in India and in Kashmir.

Helicobacter pylori

Helicobacter pylori (Gram negative bacterial infection which is prevalent in Kashmir due to unhygienic life style.

Sedentary lifestyle

Changing lifestyle and dietary habits some patients were taking fast food regularly. By the adoption of Westernized diets and lifestyles also perform a big part in the growing of incidence rate of cancer in Kashmir.

Genetic and hereditary reasons

Some patients have cancer in their family history. This is also a major reason for growing cancer in Kashmir region.

Preheating of foods is common in Kashmir

Foods are prepared usually for two time i.e. for dinner and next day lunch. During heating of food again and again nutritive value of food is decreased and carcinogenic products are formed. Patients were found to fall in this category. Cancer risk increases through this method of eating. Freshly prepared food should be consumed in order to be away from such diseases like cancer.

Use of chemicals, fungicides

Another risk factor responsible for disease of cancer is spraying of chemical and fertilizer without proper protocol means without proper veiled clothes, eating drinking and smoking while spraying is the most common factor for carcinoma.

Inhalation of petroleum products

Inhalation of petroleum products smoke, wood shavings, sawdust also increases risk for cancer for high motor vehicles drivers, carpenters, painters. About 9 % patients in present study were having this type of risk factor for cancer.

RESULTS:

After recorded all the contributory reasons via questionnaire & interview method. The observations were analysed. It was found that all

the patients were 18-80 age group. 5% were of this 18-40 age group. Rest patients were 45-80 age group. 82% patients were uneducated & 18% were educated. 79% were from rural areas and 21% were from urban areas. Different types of gastrointestinal tract cancer were admitted such as oesophagus cancer, stomach cancer, colorectal cancer, pancreas cancer, liver cancer, gallbladder cancer (%age is given in pie chart 1) also bar diagram (2). Various contributory reasons were recorded and analysed which are shown in table number (2) and also in bar diagram number (1).

Table: 2 Major contributory reasons for growing of cancer

Reason	Percentage
Smoked and salted food (meat, chicken, fish and pickles)	90%
Low consumption of fruits and vegetables	72%
Consumption of red meat	60%
Sedentary lifestyle	45%
Smoking hukkah and cigarette	80%
Delayed treatment	37%
Non-vegetarian food	100%
Use of adulterated spices	75%
Refined cereals and oils	100%
Dietary habits	90%
Wazwan	55%

Table: 3 Incidence Rate of Cancer

Oesophageal Cancer	18%
Stomach Cancer	28%
Colorectal Cancer	26%

Gallbladder Cancer	16%
Liver Cancer	7%
Pancreatic Cancer	5%

DISCUSSION:

The incidence rate of cancer varies from country to country. Sometimes, it is seen that developed countries have high rate of cancer as compared to developing countries because of their dietary patterns and western lifestyles. Cancer is a disease which generally occur in middle and old age. Twenty five percent cases of cancer in emerging nations are due to the genetics. Several studies have been done on the dietary pattern and risk

factors of cancer going in Kashmir as we are familiar that Kashmiri people have wrong nutrient deficient dietary patter also life style is not good. As for this study which is going on, it has been found that there is dramatic shift in all the risk factors and is increasing day by day. Breakfast culture is not good in Kashmir and schedule timing of eating is totally differing from other states of Kashmir that’s why there are higher gastrointestinal tract cancer patients in Kashmir as compared to rest of states. Kashmiri people take

hot beverage (salt tea boiled in open utensils), both in morning and evening time. Both males and females in rural Kashmir involve in old Kashmiri smoking habit known as “hukkah” (known as jejeer in Kashmir) and this study found young patients were smoking Hukkah which is also a possible risk factor for the disease cancer. Growing cancer cases in Kashmir is a matter of concern for this region of India. Health education and awareness is must for the rural people in order to lower its risk factor because rural people neglect the early symptoms of the disease. In 2018, Indian Government launched “Ayushman Bharat Yojana”. Under this initiative Health and Wellness were created by upgrading existing Sub Centres and Primary Health Centres. These Health and Wellness Centres have provision to detect and screen non-communicable diseases like cancer and diabetes. This initiative of Government of India can benefit rural people at large scale who are suffering from such diseases. Early detection of cancer can save millions of lives of the people. People should be aware about the early symptoms of the cancer and should not delay the treatments. Healthy lifestyle promotion camps by the governments can also help the rural people to get awareness about various diseases. Some surveys have recommended that the form of high risk of gastrointestinal cancer in Kashmir region is due the lifestyles and socio cultural and religious customs of this area of India. Education level is low in rural Kashmir. Due to the increasing rates of smoking in young people, the incidence level of cancer may further rise in future. Government can also run proper educational guidance camps for young generation to avoid the use of drugs. Campaigns are needed to educate those people who are involved in agriculture and horticulture practices to prevent the excessive use of pesticides and chemicals. A collaborative effort between healthcare professionals, policymakers and community is necessary to combat gastrointestinal

cancer and improve health outcomes in Kashmir region of India. However, it is becoming difficult to control the disease because patients are avoiding early symptoms visit to a healthcare specialist and hence focusing healthcare when the disease is at palliative mode. Now, it is very difficult to curb these diseases because it needs collective approach from government to sponsor and educates community via various sources. Broader aspect of this study is currently under progress and we need further studies on this topic so that cancer both prevalences and incidence can be controlled

CONCLUSION

As the gastrointestinal tract cancer rate is alarming in Kashmir its pertinent to all the stakeholders to research in this field and organise various seminars, conferences along all the districts of Jammu & Kashmir so that nutritional knowledge will be given at broader level. It's a task for medical fraternity to come with up with a plan alongside with government. Include work force in terms of dieticians, nutritionists and educators on various fields. rural areas cancer wards should be installed in every sub-centres. India should focus on medicinal research to make treatment affordable.

REFERENCES

1. Qurieshi, Mariya A, Salim Khan, S.M., Masoodi, Muneer A., QurieshiUruj, Ain Quratul, Jan, Yasmeen, Haq Inaamul and Ahmad Sheikh Zahoor (2016), Epidemiology of Cancers in Kashmir, India: An Analysis of Hospital Data, Hindawi Publishing Corporation Advances in Preventive Medicine 2016, Article ID 1896761, 6 pages <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/1896761>
2. Lone, Dr Ajaz Ahmad, Peer, Faisal Ahmad, (2021), GROWING CONCERN OF CANCER IN KASHMIRI SOCIETY.A

SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE, THE JOURNAL OF ORIENTAL RESEARCH MADRAS, ISSN: 0022-3301

3. Zana H. Mahmood, Fenk M. Mohamed, Binaiy N. Faith, Abdullah A. Qadir, & Shalaw H. Abdalla (2023). Cancer publications in one year (2022); a cross-sectional study. *Barw Medical Journal*. <http://doi.org/10.58742/bmj.v1i2.30>
4. Rajput, J.M (2022) Cancer: a comprehensive review, *International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Allied Sciences*, 1 (3), 42-49
5. Dewan, K, Madan, R, Sengupta, P, & Mandal A. (2020) Diet and gastric cancer, *Oncology Journal of India*, 4 (3), 115.
6. Zhang, J, Kong Q, Zhang, J, & Guo, J. (2024) Effectiveness of nutritional support for clinical outcomes in gastric cancer patients: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Open Medicine*, 19 (1) 20241023.
7. Kapoor, D. (2021). Human energy requirements. In book: *Advance Nutrition*, Indira Gandhi National Open University, New Delhi. Pp 34-63
8. Mathur, G, Nain S. and Sharma, P. K (2015) Cancer: An overview. *Academic Journal of Cancer Research*, 8 (1), 01-09. DOI: 10.5829/idosi.ajcr.2015.8.1.9336
9. Gull Fiza, *Anthropology of Food: A study on the feeding habits of Kashmiri Muslims*, *Antrocom Online Journal of Anthropology* vol.16 n 2 (2020), 327-332- ISSN 1973-2880
10. Panakkal N & Lekshmi A, Effective lung cancer control: An unaccomplished challenge in cancer research, *CytoJournal* 2023 Aug 7; 20:16
11. Gupta Ashutosh, Puri Isha & Gupta Meenu, Patterns of Cancer in Males and Females in Jammu Region *JK Science: Journal of Medical Education & Research* Vol.23 No. 1 January to March -2021
12. Wani Ajaz Ahmad, Cancer: its symptoms, Challenges and Opportunities in Research in India: A review, *Saudi J Med Pharm Sci* 9 (1), 1-5, 2023.
13. Azar HA (1962), Cancer in Lebanon and the Near East. *Cancer*, 15:66-78.
14. An epidemiological study, (1988-1989) Cancer incidence New Delhi: ICMR; p 3-42
15. Shafiee, Maena Naman and Saleem, Sheikh Mohd (2019), Kashmiri diet and Gastric Carcinoma Epidemiology and Risk Factors: A Review.

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